

ON THE UNIFORMLY STARLIKENESS OF THE EXPONENTIAL FUNCTION

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Abstract: We introduce and study a new subclass of uniformly starlike functions by the means of the convolution involving the exponential function in the unit disk.

Keywords: Uniformly Starlike functions; Hadamard product; Linear operator; Exponential function.

I. INTRODUCTION

Let A be the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n$$

(1)

Which are analytic and univalent in the open disk $U = \{z: |z| < 1\}$

Also denote by T the subclass of A consisting of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n, a_n \geq 0$$

(2)

A function $f \in A$ is said to be in the class of uniformly convex functions of order α , denoted by $UCV(\alpha)$ if

And is said to be in a corresponding subclass of $UCV(\alpha)$ denoted by $S_p(\alpha)$ if

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - \alpha \right\} \geq \beta \left| \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} - 1 \right|,$$

$-1 \leq \alpha \leq 1$ and $z \in U$ The class of uniformly convex and uniformly starlike functions has been studied by Goodman, see [3,4] and Ma and Minda [6]. If f of the form (1) and $g(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} b_n z^n$, are two functions in A , Then the Hadamard product of f and g is denoted by $f * g$ and is given by

$$(f * g)(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n b_n z^n$$

Definition 1 we consider the following linear operator

$$Jf(z) = f(z) * \exp(z) = z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} a_n z^n$$

(3)

where, $f(z) \in A$, and has the form (1).

Now using the operator introduced in (3) we can define the following subclass of analytic function, $J * f(z)$

$$\Re \left\{ \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - \alpha \right\} \geq \left| \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - 1 \right|, z \in U$$

Now let's write $JTf(z) = J * f(z) \cap T$

The origin of such classes is introduced and studied by various authors including [1], [8], and [9].

II. MAIN RESULTS

1. Characterization Property

Theorem 1.

A function f defined by (2) is in the class $JTf(z)$ if and only if

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n!} \cdot \frac{2n-1-\alpha}{1-\alpha} |a_n| \leq 1$$

Proof. It suffices to show that

$$\left| \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - 1 \right| \leq \Re \left\{ \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - \alpha \right\}$$

and we have

$$\left| \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - 1 \right| \leq \Re \left\{ \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - 1 \right\} + (1 - \alpha)$$

that is

$$\left| \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - 1 \right| - \Re \left\{ \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - 1 \right\} \leq 2 \left| \frac{z(Jf(z))'}{Jf(z)} - 1 \right| \leq \frac{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n-1) 1/n! |a_n|}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} 1/n! |a_n|}$$

The above expression is bounded by $(1 - \alpha)$ and hence the assertion of the result

Now we want to show that $f \in JTf(z)$ satisfies (3)

if $f \in JTf(z)$ then (3) yields

$$\frac{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} n/n! a_n z^{n-1}}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} 1/n! a_n z^{n-1}} - \alpha \geq \frac{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (n-1) 1/n! a_n z^{n-1}}{1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} 1/n! a_n z^{n-1}}$$

Letting $z \rightarrow 1$ along the real axis leads to the inequality

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} (2n-1-\alpha) 1/n! a_n \leq 1 - \alpha$$

Corollary 1. let a function f , defined by (2) belongs to the class $JTf(z)$ then

$$a_n \leq \frac{1}{n!} \cdot \frac{1-\alpha}{2n-1-\alpha}, \text{ for } n \geq 2$$

Theorem 2 Let the function f , defined by (2) be in the class $JTf(z)$ then

$$\begin{aligned} |z| - |z|^2 \frac{1}{2(3-\alpha)} &\leq |Jf(z)| \leq |z| + |z|^2 \frac{1}{2(3-\alpha)} \\ 1 - |z| \frac{1}{(3-\alpha)} &\leq |(Jf(z))'| \leq 1 + |z| \frac{1}{(3-\alpha)} \end{aligned}$$

The bounds above are attained for the functions given by

$$f(z) = z - \frac{1}{4(3 - \alpha)} z^2$$

Theorem 3. Let a function f , be defined by (1.2) and

$$g(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} b_n z^n$$

be in the class $JTf(z)$. then the function h , defined by

$$h(z) = (1 - \beta)f(z) + \beta g(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} c_n z^n$$

Where $c_n = (1 - \beta)a_n + \beta b_n$, and $0 \leq \beta \leq 1$, is also in the class $JTf(z)$

Now we define the following functions $f_j(z)$, ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$)

of the form

$$f_j(z) = z - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_{n,j} z^n, a_{n,j} \geq 0, z \in U$$

(4)

Theorem 4 (closure theorem). Let the functions $f_j(z)$ ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$) defined by (4), be in the class $Jf_j(z)$ ($j = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m$) respectively. Then the function $h(z)$ defined by

$$h(z) = z - \frac{1}{m} \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{j=1}^m a_{n,j} \right) z^n$$

is in the class $Jf_{\xi}(z)$ where

$$\xi = \text{Max}_{1 \leq j \leq m} \{ \alpha_j \} \text{ with } 0 \leq \alpha_j < 1.$$

2. Results involving convolution

Theorem 5. for functions $f_j(z)$ ($j = 1, 2$) defined by (4) let $f_1(z) \in JTf_1(z)$ and $f_2(z) \in JTf_2(z)$. then $f_1 * f_2 \in TR(\eta, \lambda, \gamma)$, where

$$\gamma \leq 1 - \frac{1}{(2n - 1 - \alpha)(2n - 1 - \beta)1/n! - (1 - \alpha)(1 - \beta)},$$

Theorem 6 Let the functions $f_j(z)$, ($j = 1, 2$) defined by (4) be in the class $JTf(z)$ Then $(f_1 * f_2)(z) \in JT_{-\rho}f(z)$

3. The Integral Transform

We define the integral transform

$$V_{\mu}(f)(z) = \int_0^1 \mu(t) \frac{f(tz)}{t} dt$$

Where $\mu(t)$ is a real valued, non-negative weight function normalized so that $\int_0^1 \mu(t) dt = 1$.

Special case of $\mu(t)$ is $\mu(t) = \frac{(c+1)^{\delta}}{\mu(\delta)} t^c \left(\log \frac{1}{t} \right)^{\delta-1}$, $c > -1, \delta \geq 0$

Which gives the Komatu operator.

Theorem 7 Let $f \in J Tf(z)$ Then $V_\mu(f) \in J Tf(z)$.

Theorem 8. (radius of starlikeness) Let $f \in J Tf(z)$ then $V_\mu(f)$ is starlike of order $0 \leq \gamma < 1$ in $|z| < R_1$, where

$$R_1 = \min_n \left[\left(\frac{c+n}{c+1} \right)^\delta \cdot \frac{1-\gamma(2n-1-\alpha)}{(n-\gamma)(1-\alpha)} \cdot \frac{1}{n!} \right]^{\frac{1}{n-1}}$$

Theorem 9. $f \in J Tf(z)$ then $V_\mu(f)$ is convex of order $0 \leq \gamma < 1$, in $|z| < R_2$, where

$$R_2 = \min_n \left[\left(\frac{c+n}{c+1} \right)^\delta \frac{(1-\gamma)(2n-1-\alpha)}{n(n-\gamma)(1-\alpha)} \cdot \frac{1}{n!} \right]^{\frac{1}{n-1}}$$

III. CONCLUSION

By utilizing the Hadamard product, we introduced a new linear operator that involves the analytic functions on the unit disk and the exponential function. Consequently, we defined a new subclass of uniformly starlike functions. We investigated the characteristics of the new subclass and determined the sufficient conditions for the inclusion results. In addition, we expended the finding to involve Hadamard product. Finally, we presented a study on the integral transform and obtained various results.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Wiman, Über den Fundamentalsatz in der Theorie der Funktionen $E_\alpha(x)$, *Acta Mathematica*, **1905**, 29, 191-201. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02403202>
- [2] Wiman, Adders, Über den Fundamentalsatz in der Theorie der Funktionen $E_\alpha(x)$, *Acta Mathematica*, **1905**, 29 (1905), 191-201. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF02403202>
- [3] A. W. Goodman, On uniformly convex functions, *Ann. Polon. Math.*, **1999**, 56, 87–92.
- [4] A. W. Goodman, On uniformly starlike functions, *J. Math. Anal. Appl.*, **1991**, 155, 364–370.
- [5] W. Ma, D. Minda, convex functions, } *Ann. Polon. Math.*, **1992**, 165-175.
- [6] Stanisława Kanas, Agnieszka Wisniowska, Conic regions and k-uniform convexity, *Journal of Computational and Applied Mathematics*, **1999**, 105, Issues 1–2, Pages 327-336.
- [7] C. Ramachandran, T.N. Shanmugam, H.M. Srivastava, A. Swaminathan, A unified class of k-uniformly convex functions defined by the Dziok–Srivastava linear operator, *Appl. Math. Comput.*, **2007**, 190, 1627–1636.
- [8] F. Rønning, On starlike functions associated with parabolic regions, *Ann. Univ. Mariae-Curie-Sklodowska, Sect. A.*, **1991**, 45, 117–122.
- [9] B.A. Frasin, On certain subclasses of analytic functions associated with Poisson distribution series, *Acta Univ. Sapientiae, Mathematica.*, **2019**, 11 (1), 78–86.
- [10] B.A. Frasin, Subclasses of analytic functions associated with Pascal distribution series, *Adv. Theory Nonlinear Anal. Appl.*, **2020**, 4(2), 92–99.
- [11] B.A. Frasin, S.R. Swamy, A.K. Wanas, Subclasses of starlike and convex functions associated with Pascal distribution series, *Kyungpook Math. J.*, **2021**, 61, 99–110.
- [12] A. Amourah, B. Frasin, G. Murugusundaramoorthy, on certain subclasses of uniformly spirallike functions associated with struve functions, *J. Math. Comput. Sci.*, **2021**, 11, 4586–4598.
- [13] S.M. El-Deeb, G. Murugusundaramoorthy, Applications on a subclass of β -uniformly starlike functions connected with q-Borel distribution, *Asian-European J. Math.*, 2250158.
- [14] Salah, Jamal, Hameed Ur Rehman, and Iman Al-Buwaiqi. "The Non-Trivial Zeros of the Riemann Zeta Function through Taylor Series Expansion and Incomplete Gamma Function." *Mathematics and Statistics* 10.2 (2022): 410-418.

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- [15] Rehman, Hameed Ur, Maslina Darus, and Jamal Salah. "Graphing Examples of Starlike and Convex Functions of order β ." *Appl. Math. Inf. Sci* 12.3 (2018): 509-515.
- [16] Salah, Jamal Y., and O. M. A. N. Ibra. "Properties of the Modified Caputo's Derivative Operator for certain analytic functions." *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics* 109.3 (2014): 665-671.
- [17] Jamal Salah and Maslina Darus, On convexity of the general integral operators, An. Univ. Vest Timis. Ser. Mat. - Inform. 49(1) (2011), 117-124.
- [18] Salah, Jamal. "TWO NEW EQUIVALENT STATEMENTS TO RIEMANN HYPOTHESIS." (2019).
- [19] Salah, Jamal Y. "A new subclass of univalent functions defined by the means of Jamal operator." *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)* Vol 108 (2018): 389-399.
- [20] Jamal Y. Salah On Riemann Hypothesis and Robin's Inequality. *International Journal of Scientific and Innovative Mathematical Research (IJSIMR)*. Volume (3) 4 (2015) 9-14.
- [21] Salah, Jamal. "Neighborhood of a certain family of multivalent functions with negative coefficients." *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math* 92.4 (2014): 591-597.
- [22] Salah, Jamal, and Maslina Darus. "A note on Starlike functions of order α associated with a fractional calculus operator involving Caputo's fractional." *J. Appl. comp Sc. Math* 5.1 (2011): 97-101.
- [23] J. Salah, Certain subclass of analytic functions associated with fractional calculus operator, *Trans. J. Math. Mech.*, 3 (2011), 35–42. Available from: <http://tjmm.edyropress.ro/journal/11030106.pdf>.
- [24] Salah, Jamal. "Some Remarks and Propositions on Riemann Hypothesis." *Mathematics and Statistics* 9.2 (2021): 159-165.
- [25] Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "The consequence of the analytic continuity of Zeta function subject to an additional term and a justification of the location of the non-trivial zeros." *International Journal of Science and Research (IJSR)* 9.3 (2020): 1566-1569.
- [26] Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "An Alternative perspective to Riemann Hypothesis." *PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION* 57.9 (2020): 1278-1281.
- [27] Salah, Jamal Y. "A note on the Hurwitz zeta function." *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)* 101.12 (2017): 2677-2683.
- [28] Jamal Y. Salah. Closed-to-Convex Criterion Associated to the Modified Caputo's fractional Calculus Derivative Operator. *Far East Journal of Mathematical Sciences (FJMS)*. Vol. 101, No. 1, pp. 55-59, 2017, DOI: 10.17654/MS101010055.
- [29] Jamal Y. Salah, A Note on Riemann Zeta Function, *IOSR Journal of Engineering (IOSRJEN)*, vol. 06, no. 02, pp. 07-16, February 2016, URL: [http://iosrjen.org/Papers/vol6_issue2%20\(part-3\)/B06230716.pdf](http://iosrjen.org/Papers/vol6_issue2%20(part-3)/B06230716.pdf)
- [30] Jamal Y. Salah, A Note on Gamma Function, *International Journal of Modern Sciences and Engineering Technology (IJMSET)*, vol. 2, no. 8, pp. 58-64, 2015.
- [31] Salah, Jamal, and S. Venkatesh. "Inequalities on the Theory of Univalent Functions." *Journal of Mathematics and System Science* 4.7 (2014).
- [32] Jamal Salah. Subordination and superordination involving certain fractional operator. *Asian Journal of Fuzzy and Applied Mathematics*, vol. 1, pp. 98-107, 2013. URL: <https://www.ajouronline.com/index.php/AJFAM/article/view/724>
- [33] Salah, Jamal Y. Mohammad. "Two Conditional proofs of Riemann Hypothesis." *International Journal of Sciences: Basic and Applied Research (IJSBAR)* 49.1 (2020): 74-83.
- [34] Salah, Jamal. "Fekete-Szego problems involving certain integral operator." *International Journal of Mathematics Trends and Technology-IJMTT* 7 (2014).